

**Internal institutional review board
Of
Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution**

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Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8386210

Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution information sheet of participating.

Reviewed by the undefined professor Abdul Kareem K. Alalaimat.

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Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution information sheet of participating.

Abdul Kareem K. Alalaimat*

13 April 2023

Principal investigator: Abdul Kareem Khaled Abdul Kareem Alalaimat.

Institution: Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory.

I am chemist and poet, adventurer and discoverer, mysterious and romance, scientist and philosopher, I am Abdul Kareem K. Alalaimat. I am very honest to conduct your majesty in my organization team as the abilities of the humanity you have to improve it to be the assistant mad scientist. Which this degree is given by several steps of training in several discoveries of the Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution.

We are asking your majesty to be in the institution rules as the institution gives the improvements of the youth abilities to be as the assistant corporate mad scientist in several levels of it as it designated from the institution. As Jordan faith by us in its development procedures followed by the king of Jordan Abdullah II in the seventh discussion paper to build the new worlds of the sciences in Jordan and the Arabian

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nation, where the faith of me by my abilities come in the stories of the adventuring and the discovering of the hard problems and issues that faces as it determinend as the scientific fuctions.

This institution researches studies the determinations of the new methodologies followed in the researches nd inventions strategies and methods, where it depend on the thermodynamics chemistry analysis of the scientific fictions ideas and the hard problems and mysterious magical issues in chemistry as the hardness of the alchemy philosophical questions. Where these abilities open the big door to another world of the life to be detecting based only on the arabian and Jordanian imaginations and faith. Let me go in the another worlds.

The first step is to fill the survey and the interviews questions to followed your emotional creativity as you believe and thinking. The surveys and the interviews contain some questions classified your basic abilities to be in specific adventure of the institution and under determined training courses you need to have. As you can give the details in free areas about you in specific accurate explanations and the identifications of your faith by your self. As the surveys and the interviews done online by the emails is a-alelaimat@outlook.sa and the facebook page of the institution named by Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory.

The laws in Jordan kingdom can not help the undergraduatd students to done their studies in the jordanian universities so the interventions will be to protected the studies, to allow to me to making the study in my indtitution, and to protected some of patents applications for the major researcher only.If you agree to be in the research study, you

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will be asked to complete a survey about your basic knowledge of biochemistry, physical chemistry. his will take about 1 month. Then you will be asked to watch a video (read a story, participate in a workshop, etc.)- The activity will involve the mechanism of protection of my study, the mechanism of the allowing to my institution to done the study, and mechanism of the patents applications protecting. This should take about 1 month. Finally, you will be asked to take another survey. This survey will ask you about the clinical theiritical determination of the study to be applied. This will take about 20 days. We cannot provide you with the full details about participating now before you do so, because that may alter our research results. The full details about the research and why we did it this way will be explained to you after you finish participating. We do not believe that the research will be embarrassing or offensive to you.

The study include secret dealing with the patend information before it patented so it still sending and contiuss dealing with it to protected it If you agree to be in the research, you will be asked to complete some surveys in our research lab. We will ask you about your opinions related to physical chemistry, biochemistry, and genatics science and we will collect some demographic information, such as physical chemistry biochemistry, genatics science about you. This should take about 1month. Finally, you will be asked to complete another survey about physical chemistry, biochemistry, and genatics science. This should take about x minutes. We are not able to tell you the complete details about the research and why we are doing what we are doing that is only after the proposal and patents writing, and before you incorporate it will be published and done.

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The institution will make several events have several periods of times related to the quantity and quality of the events of the discovering and adventuring in it, by the average work days along the week by five hours per day. All the information and rights will be protected by the Jordanian judgement and the Jordanian police office as it protected by the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution polices.

Since your information is collected online in an anonymous way, we will not be able to link your responses back to you. So, your responses will remain confidential. Or Since I will not record identifiers with your information, your information will remain confidential. I will not try to re-identify the information or contact you.

Adjust the language as needed to apply to your research plan: When we collect the information from you, your name and other direct identifiers will be with the information. We will keep those identifiers on the data because the importance of these data in the research will be taken. We have put protections in place to prevent people from getting access to the information, such as password protected computers, encrypted data files, locked private rooms. We think our protections will keep your information confidential. We plan to keep the information for 2 years.

The research thesis and dissertations will be partially conducted with Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution, If you have questions, concerns, or complaints about this study or you want to get additional information or provide input about this research, please contact Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat, +962777840631/ a-alelaimat@outlook.sa.

.....
The agreement signature

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I have explained the study to your majesty, and by signing the document below, you are indicating your affirmative agreement to be in the events and team. And give the signature for the documents also.

Signature: _____

Printed Name: _____

Date: _____

.....

Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution Recruitment and Advertisement scripts

Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution Recruitment and Advertisement scripts

Abdul Kareem K. Alalaimat*

13 April 2023

Advertisement script:

Name of investigator: Abdul Kareem Khaled Abdul Kareem Alalaimat.

The purpose of the institution:

Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution is a mad home research laboratory in thermodynamics chemistry made legally for the mad scientist, illusion doctor, imaginary advisor, and undefined professor. It is a scientific fiction nature dealing with the hard problems of the natural system in the applied magical chemistry and alchemy. The institution leader is chemist and poet, adventurer and discoverer, mysterious and romantic, philosopher and scientist, is Abdul Kareem K. Alalaimat. This institution is. A personal lab made for the leader as it a bad professor. The institution get the refresh of the history of mad scientist to be applied in Jordan as the faith of Jordan by our abilities

The eligible cretaria:

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution Recruitment and Advertisement scripts

The inclusion of the institution include the educational experiences as the first step to build the abilities but it focus on the lower levels of youth educational experiences to build them strongly, and the race in the modern scientific fiction ideas and hard problem solving strategies that focus on the hard issues to solve it. The physical activities, where it give the higher abilities and humanity to specific field of chemistry studies. The emotions and imagination abilities as it build to serve the humanity requirements in building and serve Jordan faith. However, the exclusions of the institution include the higher educational levels, the ages after 40 years, the people believe by the facts not on the imaginations and emotions, as the love is the central idea of the institution.

A breif list of participation benefits:

The participation in the institution events give the participants the high skills in the sciences as the assistant mad scientist skills, and the skills and learning of the researches as the assistant researcher. It improved the participants skills by the training with the discivering by guiding, and let the participants freely identified their emotions and imaginations to be applied in the new natural world of scientific fictions. As it refresh the love of the sciences for them as it get another design for the sciences differe from the bad learning in Jordan.

The time or other commitment required of the subjects:

All of the participants and researchers can send to me to contact by using the tools are the e-mail: a-alelaimat@outlook.sa and phone number: 0777840631, from out of Jordan: +962777840631.

Recruitment script:

Hallo

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution Recruitment and Advertisement scripts

My name is Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat from Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution. I am chemist and poet, adventurer and discoverer, mysterious and romantic, I am Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat.

I send to your majesty to participate in the training courses of the discovering by guiding to publish the working in the industrial chemistry and to changing the worlds. As I send to you to participate as the assistant researcher in legal certificate give to your majesty after the several courses in the skills to improve you as the mad scientist. As you can participate as third part in my discovering and adventuring team to discover the mysterious of magical chemistry sciences by using thermodynamics chemistry magic.

Participation in this research includes taking a survey about your attitudes toward Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory, which will take approximately 15 minutes. If you agree to participate in a follow-up interview, about your view of the future of researches in Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory, that will take approximately 10 to 20 minutes. If you participate in both the survey and the interview, your total time commitment will be between 25 – 35 minutes. The other of the questionnaires and interview will be send to your majesty and the other researchers by the email to contact with you. And these interviews and surveys will be about some subtopics in the events of the institution.

Please if you have any question you can tell me by email is a-alelaimat@outlook.sa or by the phone number is +962777840631.

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution informed consent.

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution informed consent

Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat*

13 April 2023

Project title: Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution.

Principal investigator: Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat.

Summary:

The purpose of the institution is to make personal mad home laboratory for thermodynamics chemistry bad professor, where it refresh the scientific fictions in real imaginations to make all the Jordan faith I asked to be a thermodynamics chemistry bad professor get all the talents in this degree, with no needing to the long time of the other research institutions. And my participation in the institution take ten years. Il of the analysis were determiend in the primary studies that sharing with the participants if they found later so all of the patents applications of the ideas give only for ABDUL KAREEM KHALED ABDUL KAREEM ALELAIMAT, all of the foundation give only from the major sponsor. All of the results of the thesis except the patents applications share equally between all of the participant by the major rule that the research get for the major response in its priority.

The purpose of the institution:

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution informed consent.

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution is a mad home research laboratory in thermodynamics chemistry made legally for the mad scientist, illusion doctor, imaginary advisor, and undefined professor. It is a scientific fiction nature dealing with the hard problems of the natural system in the applied magical chemistry and alchemy. The institution leader is chemist and poet, adventurer and discoverer, mysterious and romantic, philosopher and scientist, is Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat. This institution is. A personal lab made for the leader as it a bad professor. The institution get the refresh of the history of mad scientist to be applied in Jordan as the faith of Jordan by our abilities.

We asking your majesty to be in the institution rules as the institution give the improvements of the youth abilities to be as the assistant corporate mad scientist in several levels of it as it designated from the institution. As Jordan faith by us in its development prosedures followed by the king of Jordan Abdullah II in the seventh discussion paper to build the new worlds of the sciences in Jordan and the arabian nation, where the faith of me by my abilities come in the stories of the adventuring and the discovering of the hrad problems and issues that faces as it determiend as the scientific fuctions.

Risks to subjects:

1. The chemicals risks and the biochemical consitions found in each experiments.
2. The analysis procesures risks of the theoritical studies.
3. The adventures risks in the problems facing in the physical objects analysis and life.
4. The polices of the studies and the badness behaviours agreements.
5. The operations managements of the institution procedures.

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution informed consent.

Potential benefits of institution:

1. Applied the emotional and faith ability of Jordan.
2. Applied the seventh discussion paper of the king of Jordan Abdullah II.
3. Applied the humanity rules and values in the arabian nation and the world.
4. Get the highest knowledge in chemistry for the primary researcher.
5. Refresh and feeding the sciences in its trainings and what its values and qualities.

Incentives for participation:

1. Improve your ability and skills to be the assitant researcher abilities with the mad scientist skills.
2. Improve your experiences in the researches as the youth researcher without need to higher certificates.
3. Improve the creativity and philosophical skills in chemistry and alchemy.
4. Applied different concepts of chemistry sciences in your life to be distinguishable.
5. Increase your ability in chemistry works.
6. Make certifiacted level in chemistry industries in different fields.

Use tissue/DNA samples for future studies:

This institution dealing with different ways of the creative thinking that may be interested in the biochemistry fields that required the tissues and DNA samples. For studies collecting biological specimens – blood, hair, DNA, etc. – where unused materials may be kept or extra materials may be collected for future research, include a

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution informed consent.

separate section asking for consent to use the specimens. The rules must be taken for that are:

1. The legal agreement with participants signatures to using their tissues and other.
2. Biomedical report about the participants medical conditions and the medicinal agreements.
3. Identified the samples and the participants by their names, types, amounts and dates.
4. Rules of using it as set by the legal institutions required the agreements.

Please, writing the agreements here and signature with the cover letter of the legally using of your biochemistry samples.

My name is (write your name here) from (write your country here) I agree and signature legally on the using of (write the sample name and amounts here) for totally using by Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution in the date is (writing the date here) I agree and on that I put my signature (write signature)

If you are injured by this research

In the event that any research-related activities result in an injury, treatment will be made available including first aid, emergency treatment, and follow-up care as needed. Cost for such care will be billed in the ordinary manner to you or your insurance company. No reimbursement, compensation, or free medical care is offered by Cornell University. If you think that you have suffered a research-related injury, contact Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat right away at +962777840631 or by email at [a-alelaimat@outlook.sa](mailto:alelaimat@outlook.sa) .

As research activities or communication with participants will involve e-mail, Please note that email communication is neither private nor secure. Though Abdul Kareem K.

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Alelaimat and his team taking precautions to protect your privacy, you should be aware that information sent through e-mail could be read by a third party.

Data sharing:

De-identified data from this study may be shared with the research community at large to advance science and health. We will remove or code any personal information that could identify you before files are shared with other researchers to ensure that, by current scientific standards and known methods, no one will be able to identify you from the information we share. Despite these measures, we cannot guarantee anonymity of your personal data. And Identifiers might be removed and the de-identified information or biospecimens used for future research without additional consent.

Information about use of your biospecimens:

Specimens collected from you for this study and information derived from your specimens will not be used to generate commercial profit. You will not share in any commercial value or other compensation from products developed using these specimens. If your study may involve whole genome sequenc

Withdrawal by investigator, sponsor and physician:

1. For researcher: if the scientific faith, scientific fictions, scientific applications can not agreed with the institution requirements in a determined level of the working, if the skills can not saved with the experiences, if you leave without signature respictions cover letter. Iam sorry, that will be withdraw.
2. For students: if you can not subjected to the rules of the studies and the homeworks applied in the class, if you has lowere degrees in the certificate

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution informed consent.

below than 50%, if you dis not still subjected to the lows of the class and the sciences rules. The withdrawing set, and Iam sorry.

3. For participants: The investigators, physicians or sponsors may stop the study or take you out of the study at any time should they judge that it is in your best interest to do so, if you experience a study-related injury, if you need additional or different medication/treatment, or if you do not comply with the study plan. They may remove you from the study for various other administrative and medical reasons. They can do this without your consent.

Statement of Consent

I have read the above information, and have received answers to any questions I asked.

I consent to take part in the study.

The full name:

The date:

The signature:

The full name of the person obtain consent: Abdul Kareem Khaled Abdul Kareem Alelaimat.

The signature of the person obtain consent: A.Olimat.

The date: 13 April 2023.

This consent form will be kept by the researcher for at least five years beyond the end of the study.

The Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution protocol

Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7826795

Instruction of the institution: Abdul Kareem Khaled Abdul Kareem Alelaimat.

Objectives:

This is the mad home laboratory of thermodynamics chemistry as the mad scientist, illusion doctor, imaginary advisor, and the undefined bad professor Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat. It's a personal institution deals with the thermodynamics chemistry researches in mysterious madness ideas and the philosophical alchemy problems generating and solving. As it provide the training courses in chemistry industries. The institution put its rules in the madness scientific fictions studies in higher quality and quantity to accumulated with Jordan faith, and the students who identified here as the research team of scientific fiction believer, and the students of the courses as it. Must courses in self development required and taken by accredited training by IBCT in self training by discovering with guiding as its reality take places in the researches and applied rules as the infrastructures of the personal institution. Its civil housing society of educations and researches in Jordan as the business development and saftey. The institution adopted sustainable approachs of Jordan helping in its environment by the scientific fiction culture and its mission, where the institution sensitizes the masses

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution protocol
Review by the mad professor Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat.

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through teaching, seminars, conferences, different competition and campaigns about conservation of environment.

Values are both taught and caught in this institution. Institution performs the believing in the humanity forces and abilities to serving their abilities and build it by the courses and the researches as it build for the humanity requirements. The institution provides training in all communication skill teaching skills, handling of ICT equipments in an efficient manner which ensures the employability of the student-teachers. The global issues in the institution belivings and the mission of it is the explosion of the youth abilities in the training and educating and planning to discovered. The planning of the future developments of the institution include more discovering and areas in the natural magic of chemistry and alchemy covered by it and reach to the higher level of the knowledge to build the abilities by strongest ways.

Background:

Several scientific fiction ideas get from the films and the stories determined them and explained some properties of the bad professors that make all abilities to serve the world and build it by the higher knowledge of their minds. The history of the scientists in the world include some scientists as the scientific fictions in some leveles but in the arabian country no any one get this value. The arabian countries build all the efforts and requirements for only the modern lowest abilities for only to serving the universities and the classical institutions in researches that give conditions for doing the researches make very harsh abilities used especially in Jordan. That will reduce the scientific approaches in the youth ideas and abilities to make all the life of them in the sciences. Howeve, this idea make in the first time in arabian countries in Jordan as Jordan believe.

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Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

The inclusion of the institution include the educational experiences as the first step to build the abilities but it focus on the lower levels of youth educational experiences to build them strongly, and the race in the modern scientific fiction ideas and hard problem solving strategies that focus on the hard issues to solve it. The physical activities, where it give the higher abilities and humanity to specific field of chemistry studies. The emotionsl and imagination abilities as it build to serve the humanity requirements in building and serve Jordan faith. However, the excludions of the institution include the higher educational levels, the ages after 40 years, the people believe by the facts not on the imaginations and emotions, as the love is the central idea of the institution.

Study timeline:

The study timeline is ten years after the establishment of it include the higher numbers of higher activities in the researches, educations, trainings, thesis writing and dissertations, problem solving, experimets and experiences. Where the timeline it has the life circle periodically to make the bad professor managements in the reality of serving Jordan faith, where each period take its required timeline include the events of the bad profesdor level in it and the solving problems events.

Study endpoint:

The Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution endpoint is the primary endpoint which is subjected to take as the highest available abilities degrease of the bad professor in thermodynamics chemistry taken and with the experiences required. And for the secondary endpoint is the ten years planned for the institution with the required amount of the problem solving.

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Procedure involves:

Forstly, the office area where in it the theoritical studies taken totally with higher magnetuides and dircetions to be analysed with the agreements with the rules of the institution in the theoritical studies as all of the keys of the active ideas done in this stage. Then the studies go to the databases of the institution and unvestigated it in several manners accredited by the institution in their abilities to be applied and complete the study after the review process, then it pass through the complete accurate analysis process for the prototypes building, observations, and experimetal parts to get the highest accuracy of its fact to be done. Then the studies will be designed in the office as the financial process taken in this stage and analysed to get the proposal of the study, then these studies go with the files to the library area of the home where it saved totally in it. Then in the long brary area will be subjected under the studies of separated the researches from the thesis and dissertations to determine the scientific experimetal parts of the researches. After that, it will be go to the home laboratory area in the home to make the experimetal part, the prototypes, the observations, and the industrial objects as it determined. Finally, the studies after it completed registered by the institution ISBN number in Jordan and published by the name of the institution and the mad professor Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat.

Data and/ or spaceman banking:

Where the studies only registere by the name of the institution and the primary researcher Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat with all of the rights and the other participants as the friends and the teams will be identified legally in the studies and determine their works.

Provisions to Monitor the Data to Ensure the Safety of Subjects:

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This will be followed ethically firstly from the Jordanian judgment law which is to determine the specific procedures and the methodologies to dealing with the chemicals in my institution Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory, then followed by the Jordanian police officers to monitoring and improving the primary procedures to give a highly accuracy of it.

Withdrawal of subjects:

Any defect occur in the rules especially the safety rules even it in minimum level will withdrawal the researcher from it under any conditions that occur by it. And the procedure will be by sending an e-mail or phone with him and the legal proceedings. And it will be withdrawn from the research by the institution laws and steps. And the other conditions that required to withdraw the researchers are the defects occur on the rules of the patented of patent applications where it only for ABDUL KAREEM KHALED ABDUL KAREEM ALELAIMAT, the negligences in the study of the thesis. All of the laws, directions and orders from the instructor of the thesis research.

Risks to subjects:

1. The chemicals risks and the biochemical conditions found in each experiments.
2. The analysis procedures risks of the theoretical studies.
3. The adventures risks in the problems facing in the physical objects analysis and life.
4. The policies of the studies and the badness behaviours agreements.
5. The operations managements of the institution procedures.

Potential benefits of institution:

1. Applied the emotional and faith ability of Jordan.

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3. Applied the humanity rules and values in the arabian nation and the world.
4. Get the highest knowledge in chemistry for the primary researcher.
5. Refresh and feeding the sciences in its trainings and what its values and qualities.

Community-Based Participatory Research

1. Building a huge net in the sciences in the world to accumulated between the sciencea and the humanity and community needings and requirements.
2. Especially recognise the researches and the discovering in the humanity identity.
3. Plannings to improve the strengths of the community resources of the humanity and its highest abilities.
4. Insertion and growth the Jordan faith in the sciences and the students as the adventurer teams.

Sharing of results with subjects:

The study sharing the information after the adventure finished by registre the dissertations of the discovering and the atories in the ISBN number of the books required and printed, then the researches registrations in the journals. After theta the sharing done by using the social media.

Economic Burden to Subject

The huge budgets reured to financing the adventures and the discovering in the youth faith of the teams and the required of the safty rules and the studies. These financial problem will be solved by self training in the relationships making with the available

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sources of funding as the financial bodies. And the huge area of the financing is by the personal financing. As the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution remark as the non-profit institution of the home researches laboratory.

Drugs and devices:

- ✓ I confirm that all investigational drugs will be received by the Investigational Drug Service (IDS). The IDS will store, handle, and administer by authorized investigators.
- ✓ I confirm that all investigational devices will be labelled in accordance with FDA regulations and stored and dispensed in such a manner that they

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13 April 2023

Principal investigator: Abdul Kareem Khaled Abdul Kareem Alalaimat.

Institution: Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory.

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The first step is to fill the survey and the interviews questions to followed your emotional creativity as you believe and thinking. The surveys and the interviews contain some questions classified your basic abilities to be in specific adventure of the institution and under determined training courses you need to have. As you can give the details in free areas about you in specific accurate explanations and the identifications of your faith by your self. As the surveys and the interviews done online by the emails is a-alelaimat@outlook.sa and the facebook page of the institution named by Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory.

The laws in Jordan kingdom can not help the undergraduatd students to done their studies in the jordanian universities so the interventions will be to protected the studies, to allow to me to making the study in my indtitution, and to protected some of patents applications for the major researcher only.If you agree to be in the research study, you

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will be asked to complete a survey about your basic knowledge of biochemistry, physical chemistry. his will take about 1 month. Then you will be asked to watch a video (read a story, participate in a workshop, etc.)- The activity will involve the mechanism of protection of my study, the mechanism of the allowing to my institution to done the study, and mechanism of the patents applications protecting. This should take about 1 month. Finally, you will be asked to take another survey. This survey will ask you about the clinical theiritical determination of the study to be applied. This will take about 20 days. We cannot provide you with the full details about participating now before you do so, because that may alter our research results. The full details about the research and why we did it this way will be explained to you after you finish participating. We do not believe that the research will be embarrassing or offensive to you.

The study include secret dealing with the patend information before it patented so it still sending and contiuss dealing with it to protected it If you agree to be in the research, you will be asked to complete some surveys in our research lab. We will ask you about your opinions related to physical chemistry, biochemistry, and genatics science and we will collect some demographic information, such as physical chemistry biochemistry, genatics science about you. This should take about 1month. Finally, you will be asked to complete another survey about physical chemistry, biochemistry, and genatics science. This should take about x minutes. We are not able to tell you the complete details about the research and why we are doing what we are doing that is only after the proposal and patents writing, and before you incorporate it will be published and done.

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The institution will make several events have several periods of times related to the quantity and quality of the events of the discovering and adventuring in it, by the average work days along the week by five hours per day. All the information and rights will be protected by the Jordanian judgement and the Jordanian police office as it protected by the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution polices.

Since your information is collected online in an anonymous way, we will not be able to link your responses back to you. So, your responses will remain confidential. Or Since I will not record identifiers with your information, your information will remain confidential. I will not try to re-identify the information or contact you.

Adjust the language as needed to apply to your research plan: When we collect the information from you, your name and other direct identifiers will be with the information. We will keep those identifiers on the data because the importance of these data in the research will be taken. We have put protections in place to prevent people from getting access to the information, such as password protected computers, encrypted data files, locked private rooms. We think our protections will keep your information confidential. We plan to keep the information for 2 years.

The research thesis and dissertations will be partially conducted with Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution, If you have questions, concerns, or complaints about this study or you want to get additional information or provide input about this research, please contact Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat, +962777840631/ a-alelaimat@outlook.sa.

.....
The agreement signature

Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution information sheet of participating.

Reviewed by the undefined professor Abdul Kareem K. Alalaimat.

© 2023 Abdul Kareem K. Alalaimat , DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7831525

I have explained the study to your majesty, and by signing the document below, you are indicating your affirmative agreement to be in the events and team. And give the signature for the documents also.

Signature: _____

Printed Name: _____

Date: _____

.....

Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution Recruitment and Advertisement scripts

Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution Recruitment and Advertisement scripts

Abdul Kareem K. Alalaimat*

13 April 2023

Advertisement script:

Name of investigator: Abdul Kareem Khaled Abdul Kareem Alalaimat.

The purpose of the institution:

Alalaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution is a mad home research laboratory in thermodynamics chemistry made legally for the mad scientist, illusion doctor, imaginary advisor, and undefined professor. It is a scientific fiction nature dealing with the hard problems of the natural system in the applied magical chemistry and alchemy. The institution leader is chemist and poet, adventurer and discoverer, mysterious and romantic, philosopher and scientist, is Abdul Kareem K. Alalaimat. This institution is. A personal lab made for the leader as it a bad professor. The institution get the refresh of the history of mad scientist to be applied in Jordan as the faith of Jordan by our abilities

The eligible cretaria:

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution Recruitment and Advertisement scripts

The inclusion of the institution include the educational experiences as the first step to build the abilities but it focus on the lower levels of youth educational experiences to build them strongly, and the race in the modern scientific fiction ideas and hard problem solving strategies that focus on the hard issues to solve it. The physical activities, where it give the higher abilities and humanity to specific field of chemistry studies. The emotions and imagination abilities as it build to serve the humanity requirements in building and serve Jordan faith. However, the exclusions of the institution include the higher educational levels, the ages after 40 years, the people believe by the facts not on the imaginations and emotions, as the love is the central idea of the institution.

A breif list of participation benefits:

The participation in the institution events give the participants the high skills in the sciences as the assistant mad scientist skills, and the skills and learning of the researches as the assistant researcher. It improved the participants skills by the training with the discivering by guiding, and let the participants freely identified their emotions and imaginations to be applied in the new natural world of scientific fictions. As it refresh the love of the sciences for them as it get another design for the sciences differe from the bad learning in Jordan.

The time or other commitment required of the subjects:

All of the participants and researchers can send to me to contact by using the tools are the e-mail: a-alelaimat@outlook.sa and phone number: 0777840631, from out of Jordan: +962777840631.

Recruitment script:

Hallo

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution Recruitment and Advertisement scripts

My name is Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat from Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution. I am chemist and poet, adventurer and discoverer, mysterious and romantic, I am Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat.

I send to your majesty to participate in the training courses of the discovering by guiding to publish the working in the industrial chemistry and to changing the worlds. As I send to you to participate as the assistant researcher in legal certificates give to your majesty after the several courses in the skills to improve you as the mad scientist. As you can participate as third part in my discovering and adventuring team to discover the mysterious of magical chemistry sciences by using thermodynamics chemistry magic.

Participation in this research includes taking a survey about your attitudes toward Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory, which will take approximately 15 minutes. If you agree to participate in a follow-up interview, about your view of the future of researches in Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory, that will take approximately 10 to 20 minutes. If you participate in both the survey and the interview, your total time commitment will be between 25 – 35 minutes. The other of the questionnaires and interview will be sent to your majesty and the other researchers by the email to contact with you. And these interviews and surveys will be about some subtopics in the events of the institution.

Please if you have any question you can tell me by email is a-alelaimat@outlook.sa or by the phone number is +962777840631.

The Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution home laboratory polices.

Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat*

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory*

a-alelaimat@outlook.sa

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8330485

Vision

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory vision conclude by the stars of steps are:

1. Saturation of the imaginary applied chemistry by the Arabian cultural musical authenticity of the Arabian literature.
2. The discovering of the mysterious magical alchemy culture by applied physical chemistry and thermodynamics chemistry conceptual analysis.
3. Advisory in adventure of the metaphysics of applied chemistry sciences and subjects.
4. Applied the rules of Jordan vision in the seventh discussion paper.

Mission

The mission of Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory is the talents of the challenges in the curiosity of the applied chemistry functionalizes to the metaphysical nature of the new age of the world to judge the universe. And the imaginations to applied the reality of the nature and the hyper knowledge concentrated in the applied chemistry.

About institution

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution is a mad home laboratory designated in Jordan, Almafraaq, Az-zunayyah which is the first ideal institution in Jordan for research of life in the imaginary madness of chemistry to solving its magical properties and deals with the metaphysics of chemistry. As will as it connected to other parts of the city include the mosque, schools, Jordanian armed forces policies and rules, and the family home.

Salient Features

1. Advisory in thermodynamics chemistry and physical chemistry in the hyper knowledge and cultures of the modern Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory visions.
2. Professor college assistant for the advance college level courses in teaching and training in the modern age views.
3. Reality sciences that controlled the world culture and improve its level in the hyper universe analysis and idealizing.
4. Research and improvements the human sources and the idealizing thinking methodologies to the excellent world.
5. The judge the world by the madness home laboratory in applied chemistry.
6. Library of new sciences in the field of the applied physical chemistry and thermodynamics chemistry give the real sciences of the new age.

7. The rules spaces of the institution in the talent's parts include the recycling, Arabian literature writings, sculptures, music
8. Institution has dedicated and experienced in the different several experiments and theoretical researches in the fields of physics, chemistry, mathematics, biology, astrochemistry, biochemistry, inorganic chemistry, organic chemistry, physical chemistry, cosmology, medicine, geology.
9. Internet and computerized information repository in open science websites, and technology functionalizes in the research and improvements. Related to simulations and teaching.
10. Soft skills and hard skills designing and certifies with accreditations related to human resources and professional improvements.
11. Incubator and innovation center of the self-internal laboratory managements and feedback with excellent resolutions.
12. Benevolent management, decentralized democratic approaches and decision making; emphasis on faculty development and welfare, thrust on perspective planning and auditing.
13. Several branches industrial companies to fanning the results and outcomes from the business of the ideas.
14. Net of social media and communications to feedback examination and feedback formulations.
15. The personal hyper independent sovereignty rules in the applied sciences.
16. The guiding of emotional thinking, dreams, hopefulness rules, love and patients, killer curiosity of the modern real applied chemistry and sciences.

17. Philosophy of chemistry in the fields of the different braches of philosophy and improvements of it in the personal new age controlling of the world cultures to taken chemistry and sciences.

Academic policies

Scope of Academic Policies and Procedure Manual

This Manual is meant to serve as reference for all policies and procedures that impact academic conduct of the institute. It has been framed following the procedures and guideline Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory educations, accredited college professor Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat. In the new modern courses accredited globally.

These policies are subject to review and change as per the needs of time and keeping academic interest and priorities of the institute in mind. Any changes will be notified and enforced without any discrimination. Where firstly it will be taken the first stage at online accredited educations and training then it will be applied in the colleges offline and independent college.

Holly rules of Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution is to make the infrastructure for the students based on the combination of the Jordan principal and the feeding of the Jordan judgement as the letter send to all the world to face the hyper universe creatures, and it based on the mysterious and magical sciences and its nucleus of the applied history that combined the reality with the metaphysics to the reaching to the hyper knowledge of what we defined the applied chemistry. It deals with the personal accredited courses for the educations in its visions and missions.

Overall student's development is monitored by mentoring system with the objectives to provide guidance and support to the students, to improve student- teacher relationship,

to improve overall performance of the students and to help students in identifying various options for their career and future. Taking into consideration student centric learning process and in order to bridge the curricular gaps, various curriculum enrichment programs through add-on courses, guest lectures, seminars, workshops, etc. shall be designed in discussion.

Academic Monitoring System

Program committee members and HODs shall monitor academic practices for:

- ⟨Conduct of prescribed theory and practical by subject teacher
- ⟨Course content and its effective delivery
- ⟨Usage of different pedagogical teaching methods
- ⟨Unbiased evaluation in continuous assessment and examinations
- ⟨Syllabus completion
- ⟨Student attendance
- › Improvement in Student Performance

Conduct of theory / practical classes

- ⟨Prepare lecture-wise lesson plan / practical plan and follow it strictly.
- ⟨Prepare course content
- ⟨Share course materials with students through DPU ERP Portal.
- ⟨Promote higher cognitive learning modules in the class including experiential learning, participative learning and problem-based learning.

Mentoring policies

1. Monitoring the safety rules and Jordanian judgements and principles.
2. Monitoring the management of the institution.

3. Monitoring the quality of the laboratory and its equipment and tools.
4. Monitoring the quality of the infrastructures in different institution branches.
5. Monitoring the education values and the students feedback.
6. Monitoring the time lines and productivity of the literatures.

Research policies

The system:

The research system is carried out according to a mechanism far from indoctrination or systematic learning, and it is the result of the courses owned by the institution in the name of the primary researcher, Abdul Karim Khaled Abdul Karim Al-Alimat. This system is to find another science that lies under universal laws different from the information found in the archive of scientific databases by interpreting it in a manner illogical. One begins to work like a mad scientist in which things are looked at with their strangeness without relying or asserting confirmation of what is stated in the data in the secondary archives in the relevant field, where it begins through general observations of some things with the five senses, the five senses are discredited with the existence of the sixth sense and this is done. Denying the rules found in classical and modern science. Later, philosophical skepticism is used to explain these natural phenomena into the existence of supernatural forces, and at this stage the basic information and main keys in the study are achieved. Later, these phenomena are studied based on the imaginary doctor of the primary researcher, who is given this status in dealing with theoretical studies in the institution, so they are completely filtered with the presence of pure scientific and methodological foundations in theoretical and analytical studies only, and theoretical research methods are used at this stage. Later,

the researcher is placed under the name of the anonymous professor, Where he begins his story in scientific research and finds several events that fall within the circle of abnormal research on basic rules and begins to filter them until a large number of these events are included and classified as higher information in which he is given the status of an anonymous professor and these studies are included in the scientific thesis. Later, the researcher is placed under the permanent status, in addition to the permanent status of the anonymous professor, in the capacity of an imaginary advisor, who is the one who holds the number of questions and events and their answers with the basic keys only.

The polices:

1. The safety rules in the laboratory.
2. Home safety rules.
3. Environmental safety.
4. Personal safety.
5. Protection of laboratory parts.
6. Laboratory infrastructure protections.

Grievance Redressal Mechanism

Institutions

It's the mad home research dealing with the education of its books as the accredited academia courses in new age of real sciences, that take its rules online and offline. And dealing with the metaphysics and reality researches in different several parts of applied chemistry and other branches and related subjects. As it dealing with the recycling to make the green house of applied laboratory based on some strange abilities and decors,

as depend on the talents feeding of the new real metaphysics sciences in the field of the applied chemistry, and it related to the music, Arabian literature, and sculpturing.

Instruments

Its recycling, modern real, and common life using instruments.

Internal management Policy

The institution is located, under the mechanism of a school, in dedicated transactions, starting from the roof of the administration, then passing through the areas adjacent to it, which is first the office space, where theoretical research is studied purely in accordance with the foundations and laws of the institution. These studies pass through the databases and are examined and analyzed after the study. The multifaceted theory, in order to memorize general safety rules and minute details in the home laboratory space. This theoretical study then goes through comprehensive planning of prototypes, observations and practical experiments at the end of the theoretical study and after recording it. Later, it goes through the management space to feed it with the appropriate financial support to conduct practical experiments, prototypes, and observations. Then, this study is sent with the detailed work project to the institution's library, where it settles in a file that records this complete theoretical study, so it is initially preserved and stored. Then this study is transferred to the stage of writing scientific research in the library, so the research required for this study is written and preserved entirely in the institution's library, in order to add practical study details to it and feed it with experiments. This research, along with the detailed work project, passes to the home laboratory space, where preliminary experiments, observations, and prototypes are made. Then it goes through industrial studies in the laboratory, which have been

theoretically completed, so the required compound or device is prepared. The work in the laboratory goes through the initial procedure, which is the conditions of public safety, then the material and tools room is opened in accordance with the security orders in the country, then the required experiments are studied, and they are transferred to the administration and the library, they are attached within the theoretical studies and then published in the name of the institution and the main researcher Professor Unknown Abdul-Karim Khaled Abdul-Kareem Alelaimat, where the unknown professor takes the status of leader within the institutional campus of the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory

All the areas except the laboratory area build as electronic repositories to keep the area of the home as the mad home laboratory.

Green Campus and Environment Policy

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory is a place where environmental friendly practices and education combine to promote sustainable and eco-friendly practices in the campus, and it dealing with green chemistry talents. That include:

1. To continuously improve the efficient use of all resources, including energy and water.
2. To reduce consumption and the amount of waste produced.
3. Recovering and recycling waste where possible.
4. To make the campus plastic free.
5. To conduct environmental and energy audits from time to time.
6. Design less hazardous chemical syntheses.
7. Design safer and challenges improvements in chemicals and products.
8. Recycling rubbish materials to reuse it in the lab parts.

9. Using less papers and depend on online repositories and files in computerized strategies.
10. Using less coasts chemicals and high costs products.
11. Use environment components such as natural chemicals to reduce the synthetic chemicals needings.

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory Protocol

Abdul Kareem K. Alelaimat*

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory*,

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8385775

Abstract:

This work is done for the new entrepreneurship company building strategies in applied chemistry as a part of the Laboratory Project in Jordan university of science and technology. The protocol focusing on the building strategies of the company in Az-zunayyah town in Jordan, it depend on the characterization of the study as the geochemistry, environment chemistry, green chemistry, analytical chemistry, surveys, and case studies. This protocol contain six procedures for each part of the study methodology. As it's the study determined for the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution Philosophy thesis.

Introduction:

The world go towards the new idea in Corona virus pandemic in the bachelor student teaching for the laboratory in applied chemistry in some countries. This idea is the home-based laboratory that was found in the ancient scientists and philosophy, and this idea will be activated in Jordan as the first time applied in Jordan as set in Az-zunayyah

town in Almafraq city. However, the idea application based on the seventh discussion paper of the king of Jordan Abdullah II bin AL Hussain. And the institution building to make my ideas, hopeness, love, patience, and curiosity act really and imaginary. This protocol is applied for the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory infrastructure building as the research home-based laboratory include the literature review of the madness laboratory modern ideas and applications.

Materials and methods:

Monkey survey, facebook, 200g soil, brass plate in the GOR by the thickness 1cm, width is 20 cm and length is 30cm, ground penetration radar, 1m sand, thermometer, gas chromatography, ice, hot plate, 7000ml distilled water, Li, Na, Fe, Co, Cu, As, Cl, Al, F lumps, atomic absorption spectroscopy, gelatin, veniger, saucepan, anemometer, refrigerator, drill tools for well building, camera, gloves, google earth, recycling container, interview papers, traffic money costs.

Procedure:

In this section the procedures data will be determined for the study so go to it; firstly the survey procedure, where in seven questions available to be answered by no or yes in the determined especial questionnaire for specified in Arabian language with good background of the new idea to be taken, and these questions are:

Note: "Th home-based laboratory is a new idea come from Corona virus pandemic to solve the problem that there is no available sharing working between student, and I make as the entrepreneurship idea based on new world and on the seventh discussion paper of King Abdullah II bin AL Hussain, and based on the using of home chemicals and instruments to make Arabian culture with Arabian character of undefined professor."

- Are the mission of you agree with building home-based laboratory?
- Are your vision agree with the building of new home-based laboratory?
- Does it caused any defects in the town function, or on you?
- Does it help to feed your culture and growth for it?
- Are it caused toxic and hazardous feelings on your policies?
- Are you give me the chance to explore the universe?
- Are you want to become a one of the team?

Then the environmental chemistry will be set and taken as the procedure below:

1. The soil type:

- Soil colloids:

Get the beaker mass then add 25 g of soil, add to 200 ml distilled water, then avoiding the foaming add 10-20H₂O₂, then leave it at room temperature for 2 days. After that, heat to 80°C in the fume hood to remove the H₂O₂. Then dry in oven for 24 hours at 105°C, then using graduated cylinder and blank sample (1:99 soil to distilled water) then mix the soil (suspension) and left it for 10 second then insert the hydrometer, after that, record reading at each 20seconds five times then make the average.

- Soil cation and anion exchange:

Divided the earth into specific areas by 1m² then take from each one from the center a sample by 5 g, mix the samples then take 1 g from the mixture. Then will be add to it drops of water in porcelain dish and drops of 10% HCl add, if bubbles appear the soil is carbonate. Then take another 2 g sample of soil in test tube with 10ml HCl with 0.2 M, then

after that shaken then filtrate then add 2% BaCl₂ and shaken then the white precipitates of BaSO₄ appear so it gypsum. For another sample getting from soil use 1g soil and 5 g distilled water then shaken for 3 minutes then filtrate, add 10% H₂SO₄ drops then few drops of 5% AgNO₃ and shaken, if appear white precipitate of AgCl then it salty

- Soil acidity:

The land must be designed to be in 1 m² imaginary, then take from each area a one gram of soil from the center to collect 10 g soil, then mix it and take a sample of 1 g. then make the solution from it by distilled water and mix the solution carefully by the volume is 50ml. Put the pH device column then measure the results, by using the curve of the calibration scale measure the acidity of the soil.

- Soil salinity:

Drying soil at 105°C for 24 hours, then take 200g of it then put it in container with lid and saturated it by deionized water to become saturated, then let the equilibrium occur for 4 hours, then if there is water add soil and if there is soil dried add water in saturation state. After that, take it for other 4 hours then make filtration by Büchner funnel and extract soil by centrifuge. After that, put the conductivity electric cell column in it and read the EC.

2. The water available:

- If there is groundwater. By using ground-penetrating radar, connect it with USB with laptop, using the object of brass plate in the GOR by the thickness 1cm, width is 20 cm and length is 30cm. And make the trench

by length is 100cm, and width is 50cm and by the sand layer put by the depth is 1cm. Then make the exploration and determine the graph.

- If there is no groundwater. Make the ground well and filled it by the water sources such as the winter, make the tap also as the source directly connected to the ground well.

3. The heat range:

- By using thermometer clean it by distilled water then dry it, then make it free in the air without connections.
- Take the temperature value at each hour from 6 o'clock to the second day at 6 o'clock then set it in the table.
- Take different reading in the sides of the area surrounding the institution place, and in the entrance of the surrounding. Then scaling it carefully.

4. The air system and components ratio:

- The sample will be collecting from different areas in Az-zunayyah and from the institution place for different days at different temperatures by using sampling pump.
- Using the gas chromatography: the sample injected in the port by the hypodermic syringe, then heated until gas phase transfer to the column by the carrier gas (Helium), once the chromatogram appear determined the types of the gases and its amount with ratio.

5. Trace elements in the water:

- Take sample of the water from its sources by the lid of the bottle in different times (morning, afternoon...) and different days (cold, hot), one from the top of the ground wells, then from the depth distance, then

saved in the refrigerator until it transfer to the lab. The total sample is 500 ml.

- Take 50 ml filtered water then make it cold at -5°C , then measure the pH and calculate the curve with the heat of it, then determine the first point, the point in cold medium, and the point in the hot stage as the highest level of temperature in the town.
- Take 50 ml of water then add to it the tablespoon of vinegar, then boil it in the saucepan, make solution of unsaturated sugar/water then add it to the water, add two gelatin sheets to water until it dissolved, cooling agar for few hours. Take 50 sample of water, and set the candle around the system to avoid the air bacteria, then zigzag put some points of water on the agar and put the lid, set it for 5 days in a warm condition, then each points appear is a bacteria position.
- Take 5 ml of water. Take the lumps of the ions from the atoms are (Li, Na, Fe, Co, Cu, As, Cl, Al, F) then put the sample of the water and put it on the nebulizer and set the graph to detecting the salts ions.

1. Geographical analysis of the town and the institution:

- By using google earth and google maps, determine the map of Az-zunayyah and the position of the institution building, determine the mountains, the valleys, the plains, and buttes.
- By using google earth and anemometer determine the map of winds for the season with its name and determine these requirements on Az-zunayyah map and the institution position. These are:
 - The wind flow speed, the wind flow direction. And the wind flow strength.

Using the anemometer, place 100 m from the entrances of the institution place and measure the speed of winds, then set in the center of the place area and measure it by connected the anemometer to the laptop by USB and set the ter then Where wends direction is the rotation numbers, strength is the velocity of the rotation number, the direction is the angular position of the device.

- The winds flow density.

That is from the mole fractions % in the gas chromatography for the air, then convert it to mass and divided it by the volume, then multiplied it by the speed of winds cubic and divided by 2.

Then green chemistry will be set and take as the procedure below:

1. The rubbish ratio:

Calculate and take photos for the rubbish positions and determine the distributions with the ratio of the rubbish mass per area.

2. The rubbish quality: (inorganic, organic)

Take gloves and separate the rubbish surrounding the institution and the town then determine each of the organic materials in specific container and other for inorganic materials. Then physical process of crashing and separating of the sample set. Then take samples of the mixture after several mixing, then take the specral analysis.. The rubbish decomposition ratio:

The rubbish go to non-chemically process will be recycling and saved in another container. Must flow in the rules of the Trusted and high product sales exposure.

3. The rubbish goes to the recycling or no.

That can be recycling formulate the protocols of the recycling and new project to manufacturing it with the SWOT analysis for that. That can not goes to recycling write it with its ratio and distribution to be registered in the institution and send copy for the environment policemen, the head of the town, the municipality, as publish it publically.

Then the ethnography, where it will be used as the procedure below:

1. The mission ethnography analysis.

"The mission of Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory is the talents of the challenges in the curiosity of the applied chemistry functionalizes to the metaphysical nature of the new age of the world to judge the universe. And the imaginations to applied the reality of the nature and the hyper knowledge concentrated in the applied chemistry."

2. The vision ethnography analysis.

" First rule is the saturation of the imaginary applied chemistry by the Arabian cultural musical authenticity of the Arabian literature. Second rule is the discovering of the mysterious magical alchemy culture by applied physical chemistry and thermodynamics chemistry conceptual analysis. Third rule is the advisory in adventure of the metaphysics of applied chemistry sciences and subjects. Fourth rule is the applied the rules of Jordan vision in the seventh discussion paper."

The case study will be taken also include the agreements and the grants required, where its procedure is: include the laboratory building engineering also.

- Agreements.

A cover letter sends to the police office in Bala'ma, and the Almafraaq judgement include the mission of the institution and vision summary, and the safety rules of the institution with the policies of the institution.

- Grants.

E-mail sending with the cover letter and the proposal of the institution to the grants bodies in Jordan and global.

- Engineering building.

Simple mathematics, simple physics, and applied chemistry will be taken to design a new building for the applied chemistry and thermodynamics chemistry home-based laboratory focusing on the studies.

Data analysis methods

In this section I will investigated the data analysis methods used in the procedure application for the protocol of Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution philosophy that will be applied here in the chapter of the research studies results and discussions, and in this section I will get the good analysis of the calculations and steps of analysis spectral data as I will get the understanding of the procedure that will be used with the profile of the institutions in applied chemistry as the home-based laboratory building in Jordan, Az-zunayyah.

1. The survey of the public people in Az-zunayyah data analysis.

In this part data of the survey will be collected and make the diagram of the results in answers of yes and no, then the data will take its average and main values, set as the accuracy getting and the precision, then prepared the agreements of the people and disagreements and get each question in the survey a specific value by using the average value to evaluate the strength of the answers, then collect the strengths of them and take

the main and average values to compare it with the simple answers values and get the final agreements from the public. That will be designed in the institution profile and registered electronically by digital object identifier for the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory library as the reference profile.

2. The ethnography of the mission and the vision.

That will be separate each target and sentences from the vision and the mission, then get its values from the ethnography analysis of the values of its, then take the average and the main values, then multiplied each part with the values to get the strength of them, and then take the average and main for them and determined the accuracy with the precision of the world idea, then it will be saved as the institution profile and registered by the digital object identifier electronically.

3. Green chemistry.

Collect the rubbish quality with its ratio and determine for each one if it will be recycling, then measure the tendency to behave as the chemical recycling. Put the data in scale and determine the main and average values for the quantity for its variables of the ratio and tendency, then determine the strength of them by multiplied each value with the average and take the main values. After that, determined high quality materials, the high product and trusted materials, then the determination of the costs and the ratio acting, then the set of economics SWOT.

4. Environment chemistry.

- For the soil:
 - Soil salinity:

Take the values of the E_c of the samples for five times, record it in the table, then make the average value and the main value with the accuracy setting.

- Soil colloids:

Record the values for the hydrometer for five times after each 20 seconds, then take the average of the values and mentioned it with the accuracy of the study.

- Soil cations and anions exchange:

In the first step if bubbles appear the soil is carbonate. In the second step if the white precipitates of BaSO_4 appear so it gypsum. In the third step if appear white precipitate of AgCl then it salty.

- Soil acidity:

Drawing the pH diagram then take the pH value for the water in the endpoints, then determine the pH total value. Take the average and mean values, then determine the pKa value and the acidity of the water.

- For the air:

- The spectra reading for the chemicals in the air by the peaks determination, where each peak corresponding to specific atom, then search about it in the encyclopedia or in the references available data tables of the atoms in Gas Chromatography to determine each atom.
- The spectra reading for the amounts of each chemical by the length of each peaks, where it corresponds to specific concentration available in the dependent axis of the chromatogram.

- For the water:

- Water availability:

Read the spectra of ground-penetrating radar and determine if there is water, determine each of the water depth, sub-bottom sediment thickness, surface water/ground water

connection. And take the results. And if there is no ground well use the industrial ground make building with the source of the water as the tap on it, but must taken the water studies.

- Chemical compositions:

Firstly if the appear in the agar a porous points so there is bacteria ratios in the water. And the spectra of the water from the atomic absorption spectroscopy show the types of the elements of the salts in ion phase as the peaks, where each peak represent a one metal ion and the number of beaks represent the amount of it.

- Water acidity:

Drawing the pH diagram then take the pH value for the water in the endpoints, then determine the pH total value for it at specific required temperature for (-5°C, 0°C, 27°C, and 40°C). Take the average and mean values, then determine the pKa value and the acidity of the water.

- For the heat:

- Temperature range, main and average values, of the day and night.
- Temperature mapping of the surrounding.

Take the photo of the surrounding map, then determined the points of the measurements locations, then set the average temperature in each position and the location.

5. The case study.

- The agreements:

- Analyze are the basic requirements for the laboratory techniques and the methodologies of its working.
- Analyze possibility of the laboratory building in the town.

- Agreements level and protections:
 - Analyze policies detecting results:
 - Analyze agreements requirements (Documents, money, physical objects)
- The grants:

The grants determined by business proposal set by Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory and determine the mechanism of the managements system and design. And the library printed it, the proposal sent to the financial bodies in Jordan and Arabian countries as the European Union for different bodies in them. Determined the factors and the variables that are the business factors by the Canvas model analysis. Where the customer segments determined for the business, then connected by the values propositions that release to use it to identified the channels to design the customer relationships. After that, the Canvas model analysis determined the key partners to make the key resources by the key activities, and set the resume revenue and finally by the detection of the Canvas model analysis value by the costs.

- The engineering of the chemistry home-based laboratory.
 - Area of the home:

The area of the home is 49 m² and divided to four parts of it. Home is designed as a studio home, divided into four rooms one is the kitchen, the bedroom, and the living room with bathroom . With the walls surrounding the home place area and set on its top the sieve iron helical sheets and its length by the same as the home rooms lengths is 3.5 m². And Jermicula design for the walls surrounding the home, and the surface of the home to protected it, with iron doors avoid any penetration's and all the home protected by several cameras in different ways.

- Area of the lab:

According to the industry ministry of Jordan for personal home industry the maximum area for the home business is 25 m² . It take to be faraway from the lab area, take small areas of windows 20cm×1m, take iron sieve sheet for the windows and doors.

- Chemical protection methods:

The home components contain gases path, flame protection, flame protection walls painting. Moisture, temperature, pressure, winds, and other outer conditions of the home protected by the gypsum layer for heat and pressure, from winds by small windows and iron sieve sheet for the doors also by small porous, and moisture by bricks, air vents, roof ventilation tiles, ventilated soffits and window ven. Using also the water source for fire protection by water sprinkler in the top, and fire extinguisher and bathroom, with eyes washer.

6. Ethnography mission and vision:

- Thematic analysis

Become familiar with the data, generate initial codes, Search for themes, Review themes, Define themes, Write-up.

- Narrative analysis

Code narrative blocks. Group and read by live-event. Create a nested story structure. Delve into the story structure. Compare across story structure. Tell the core narrative.

- Discourse analysis

conduct detailed observations, take field notes, analyze interactions, interview key informants, conduct documentary analyses.

- Grounded theory

Firstly, the step must compare information of the vision and the mission with other from the starting of the introduction. Secondly, compare information that gathering with emerging categories. Thirdly, demonstrate relationships between concepts and categories

- Content analysis.

be immersed in the contexts, environment, situations, and lifeworld of the subjects. And the steps are ranged by coma from the first as, Decide the level of analysis, Decide how many concepts to code, Decide whether to code for existence or frequency of a concept, Decide on how you will distinguish among concepts, Develop rules for coding your texts, Decide what to do with irrelevant information, code the text, then analyze the results

Appendix one: 3D google earth map of Az-zunayyah.

Appendix two: Az-zunayyah map.

Conclusion:

This study take place in Az-zunayyah town about the new idea formation depend on the mission and vision in global community and applications and starting with different scientific research books and literature in Arabian culture and artificial intelligence. The protocol describe the mechanisms of the experiments to set it in different stages and different research methodologies types.